

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ANTITUMOR MARKERS ELIMINATION LEVELS IN THE DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF COLORECTAL CANCER AND ADENOMATOUS POLYPOSIS

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ABSTRACT

Materials of 79 patients who were examined and treated with the diagnosis of colorectal cancer and adenomatous polyps at the Oncology Clinic of Azerbaijan Medical University were included in the present study; the control group consisted of 14 healthy adults. The age of the patients varied between 36-65, 58 of them were men, and 21 were women. 10 of the healthy persons were female, and four were male. The concentration of calprotectin and cathelicidin in blood serum was carried out by immunoenzymatic method. The principle of the method is based on the use of specific antibodies against the peptide sequence of the studied antimicrobial peptides. In the research work, it is determined that the concentration of cathelicidin in the blood serum of group I patients is higher than the control limits in all patients. Hence, its concentration increases statistically reliably by 2.2 times compared to the control. The reliability coefficient of the difference is calculated as $p < 0.001$. Its average statistical value is 2.10 ± 0.09 pg/ml. The group's minimum value is 1.3 pg/ml, and the maximum value is 2.8 pg/ml.

Keywords: calprotectin, cathelicidin, colorectal cancer, AMP, cytokines.

Recently, immune mechanisms in the pathogenesis of colorectal cancer have been the focus of special attention and are widely studied. Cytokines and antimicrobial peptides (AMP) play an important regulatory role in immune mechanisms. According to the results of many studies, cytokines play an important role in the monitoring and prognosis of malignant oncological diseases [1, 2, 3, 4].

It was determined that in the development of CRC, oncogenes belonging to the family of Ras genes are activated through two main mechanisms: point mutation and amplification of H-Ras oncogenes. H-Ras is localized in different chromosomes, responsible for synthesizing the p21 protein. This protein ensures the transmission of intracellular signals of growth factors. In normal cells, this protein is inactivated after transmitting signals affecting cell proliferation and differentiation. In malignant cells, however, the p21 protein is not inactivated, and as a result, tumor cells become irregular and proliferate. Unlike oncogenes, anti-oncogenes (Rb and p53) have recessive inheritance, and their inactivation can lead to tumorigenesis. Among anti-oncogenes, the gene suppressor p53 is the most important, as it ensures programmed cell death by arresting cell division in the G0 phase, thereby reducing the risk of carcinogenesis. p53 gene mutation occurs in 9% of follicular cancer patients and 80-85% of undifferentiated histological types [5,6,7]. As a result of numerous studies has found that the weakening of the humoral immune system in patients with CRC results in an acute imbalance of many cytokines, including AMP [8, 9].

Determining Calprotectin, fecal Calprotectin, and cathelicidin play great practical importance in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant derivatives of the bowel. The study of IL-6 and TNF- α inflammatory cytokines and AMP is of great scientific and practical importance in investigating pathogenetic immune

mechanisms of CRC and adenomatous polyposis and conducting morphological and clinical-biochemical studies. Complex analysis of biochemical and immunological indicators, cytokines, and AMP during colorectal neoplasia has diagnostic information in determining the histological type and stage of the disease.

Blood from healthy individuals and patients with CRC and AP included in the contingent of the study was taken from the elbow vein on an empty stomach in the morning, in cold conditions, for 10 minutes. 2500 cycles/min. After centrifugation, it was stored at -40 degrees for two weeks.

In order to evaluate the role of immune system disorders in the pathogenesis of Colorectal cancer and adenomatous polyposis (AP), the concentration of Th-1 type cytokines (IL-6 and TNF- α) in the blood of the study contingent was examined by immunoenzymatic method. The concentration of TNF- α and IL-6 cytokines in blood serum was carried out using the "sandwich" method using the reagent kit of the company "Vector-Best" (Russian Federation). The principle of the method is based on a one-phase enzyme-linked immunosorbent reaction, and the polyclonal antibodies used are specific for the amino acid sequence of IL-6 and TNF- α peptides, allowing us to determine the investigated peptide chains. During incubation, MAb1 - IL-6 MAb2 (polyclonal biotinylated rabbit antibodies against human interleukins) - HRP complexes are formed by the principle of antigen-antibody. After the incubation period, the wells are washed with a special solution, and the chromogenic solution TMB is added to them. The amount of IL-6 is directly proportional to the intensity of the color of the solution in the cell, and the result is determined using a curve built based on the standards.

The concentration of TNF- α was determined in microplate wells coated with specific human monoclonal antibodies. As a result of the reaction, a sandwich complex is formed between monoclonal antibodies sensitive to TNF- α (MAB1) and monoclonal antibodies labeled with peroxidase (MAB2). Residual antibodies not combined with the labeled enzyme are removed with a washing solution. The intensity of the color formed by the formed complex with a specific chromogenic substance is directly proportional to the concentration of TNF- α . The concentration of TNF- α is calculated based on the standard deviation curve.

The concentration of Calprotectin and cathelicidin in blood serum was carried out by immunoenzymatic method using the reagent kit of the company "Eastbio-pharm" (Spain). The principle of the method is based on the use of specific antibodies against the peptide sequence of the investigated antimicrobial peptides and their determination by recognizing various epitopes in the polypeptide chain. The principle of the calprotectin determination method is based on the reaction of monoclonal antibodies against human Calprotectin and biotinylated calprotectin antibodies with Stretovin-HRP. During the work, 50 μ l of standard solution or serum is added to the wells, and 50 μ l of Streptavidin-HRP so-

lution is poured over it and incubated at room temperature for 60 minutes. After washing with a special solution, 50 μ l of the chromogenic solution is added. After 10 minutes of incubation at 37 degrees, the reaction is stopped with 50 μ l of sulfuric acid. To determine the concentration of Calprotectin, a calibration curve based on the intensity of the color of standard solutions is used.

Immunoenzymatic tests were performed on an immunoenzymatic analyzer Stat Fax 303 Plus (USA) (λ =450 nm, differential filter 650 nm). The concentrations of IL-6 and TNF- α in the blood serum of all groups of patients included in the study, including patients with Adenomatous polyposis, were studied. It was determined that the concentrations of IL-6 and TNF- α in the blood serum of patients with AP did not change statistically reliably compared to control levels. Thus, in this group, the concentration of TNF- α increased by 25.4% compared to the control and was 1.09 $\pm$ 0.14 pg/ml on average. Its minimum level is 0.11 pg/ml, and its maximum is 2.06 pg/ml. The concentration of TNF- α in 4 patients (16.0%) is higher than the control, and in 21 patients (84.0%), it is lower than the control (χ =2.50). Accordingly, the average concentration of TNF- α in the control group is 0.87 $\pm$ 0.20 pg/ml, and within the group, it varies within the limits of 0.28-3.07 pg/ml (table 1.0.)

Table 1.0

Concentrations of some cytokines and CEA in patients with Adenomatous polyposis

Parameters	Groups	
	AP (n=25)	Control
IL-6, pg/ml	2,82 $\pm$ 0,27 (0,9-5,0)	2,40 $\pm$ 0,36 (0,1-5,2)
TNF- α , pg/ml	1,09 $\pm$ 0,14 (0,11-2,06)	0,87 $\pm$ 0,20 (0,28-3,07)
CEA, ng/ml	1,41 $\pm$ 0,19 (0,2-3,8)	1,32 $\pm$ 0,24 (0,2-3,6)

*** - $p < 0,001$; ** - $p < 0,01$; * - $p < 0,05$

In patients with Adenomatous polyposis, IL-6, TNF- α , and CEA oncomarker concentrations, compared to the corresponding indicators of the control group, did not show a statistically significant difference. In the research work, it is known that a certain increase in the concentration of AMP in the blood serum of patients with Adenomatous polyposis is observed. The density of Calprotectin is higher than the control in 14 patients (56.0%) and lower than the control in 11 patients (44.0%) (χ =12.23, $p < 0.001$). In this group, the concentration of Calprotectin increased by 30.9% compared to the indicators of the control group and is 119.6 $\pm$ 5.5 ng/ml on average. This difference is statistically reliable, the coefficient of honesty is calculated as $p \leq 0.004$. Its minimum level is 79.9 ng/ml, and its maximum is 161 ng/ml. Accordingly, the concentration of CP in the control group varies from 67.8 to 110.6 ng/ml and is 91.4 $\pm$ 4.0 ng/ml.

Our research also determined the concentration of IL-6 in the blood serum of patients included in group I (stage I-II) of patients with Primary colorectal lymphomas. It was higher in 5 patients (17.9%) than in controls and 23 patients (82.1 %); it is lower than the control limits (χ =2.84). The concentration of IL-6 in this group increased by 41.5%, i.e., 1.4 times compared to the corresponding indicators of the control group, and is 3.40 $\pm$ 0.34 pg/ml on average.

In 6 (42.9%) Group II (carcinoid tumors) patients, IL-6 concentration is higher than the control, and in 8 (57.1%), it is lower than the control limits (χ =7.64, $p < 0.01$). In this group, the concentration of IL-6 varied between the limits of 0.9-6.8 pg/ml, and the average mathematical indicator was 4.01 $\pm$ 0.54 pg/ml (table 1.1.)

Tabel 1.1.

The concentration of some cytokines and CEA in the blood serum of patients with Colorectal cancer

Parameters	Groups		
	CRC		Control
	I-II grade(n=28)	III-IV grade (n=14)	
IL-6, pq/ml	3,40±0,34 (0,3-6,1)	4,01±0,54* (0,9-6,8)	2,40±0,36 (0,1-5,2)
TNF-α, pq/ml	1,31±0,11* (0,37-2,13)	1,65±0,23** (0,73-3,0)	0,87±0,20 (0,28-3,07)
CEA, nq/ml	2,20±0,23*,^ (0,4-4,2)	2,61±0,30**,^^ (0,8-4,3)	1,32±0,24 (0,2-3,6)

*** - $p < 0,001$; ** - $p < 0,01$; * - $p < 0,05$ – compared to control, ^^ - $p < 0,001$; ^^ - $p < 0,01$; ^ - $p < 0,05$ – compared to patients with Adenomatous polyposis

According to the results of the research, the density of CP in group I is higher than the control in 23 patients (82.1%) and lower than the control in 5 patients (17.9%) ($\chi^2=25.42$, $p < 0.001$). In this group, the concentration of CP increased by 64.6%, i.e., 1.7 times, compared to the relevant indicators of the control group, and is 150.4 ± 6.6 ng/ml. In this group, the recorded minimum concentration of KP is 92.6 ng/ml, and its maximum concentration is 206 ng/ml. According to the results of the comparative analysis, the density of CP increases by 25.8%, i.e., 1.3 times, compared to that in patients with AP. The coefficient of the integrity of this difference is calculated as $p \leq 0.002$.

The concentration of Calprotectin in the blood serum of patients in group II was higher than control limits in 13 patients (92.0%) and lower than control in 1 patient (8.0%) ($\chi^2=24.27$, $p < 0.001$). Based on the obtained results, the concentration of Calprotectin increases statistically reliably by 3.5 times compared to the control group, and the coefficient of the integrity of this difference is $p < 0.001$. The average mathematical density of this indicator is 3.42 ± 0.48 pg/ml, the minimum density is 0.7 pg/ml, and the maximum thickness is 6.1 pg/ml.

The concentration of KP in the blood serum of IV group (IV stage CRC) patients varies between 119-215 ng/ml and the average mathematical concentration is 169.7 ± 22.3 ng/ml. According to statistical calculations, CP thickness increased by 85.7%, i.e., 1.9 times statistically reliable ($p < 0.001$) compared to the control group.

The concentration of cathelicidin in the blood serum of patients in the IV group increased by 70.5%, 1.7

times statistically reliable compared to the control group, and is 108.8 ± 19.6 ng/ml on average. This difference is statistically reliable; the coefficient of honesty is calculated as $p \leq 0.044$. The concentration of cathelicidin in this group ranges from 57 to 142 ng/ml. A statistically significant increase in the concentration of CEA oncomarker in patients with papillary CRC compared to control by 76.8%, i.e. 1.8 times ($p \leq 0.007$), and by 65.4%, i.e. 1.7 times ($p \leq 0.003$) compared to patients with AP is an indicator. The concentration of CEA in this group is 2.34 ± 0.18 ng/ml, the minimum hand is 0.4 ng/ml, and the leading indicator is 4.3 ng/ml. In the follicular form, the concentration of CEA increases by 77.2%, i.e., 1.8 times ($p \leq 0.017$) compared to the control, and by 65.8%, i.e., 1.7 times ($p \leq 0.020$) compared to AP. In the research study, a more significant increase in the concentration of CP, lactoferrin, and defensin is observed among AMP. Thus, the attention of Calprotectin was on average 154.3 ± 5.9 ng/ml, 68.8%, i.e., 1.7 times ($p < 0.001$) compared to the control patients, and 29, 0%, that is, it increases with a statistically significant increase of 1.3 times ($p < 0.001$).

Based on the ROC curve of TNF-α, it is determined that its area is 0.616, and its standard error is 0.069 ($p < 0.100$). In the 95% confidence interval, the reference indicators of this indicator vary from 0.480 to 0.751. The specificity is calculated based on the ROC curve of IL-6 is 0.624. Its standard error was 0.063 ($p < 0.077$), with an honesty interval ranging from 0.501 to 0.747. CEA has an upper limit of 0.616, a lower limit of 0.845, and a specificity range of 0.731 with a standard error of 0.058 ($p < 0.00$) at the 95% confidence interval of CEA (picture 1.0)

Picture 1.0. ROC analysis of Calprotectin

Calprotectin is determined based on the ROC curve; its area is 0.776, and the standard error is 0.053 ($p < 0.001$). In the 95% confidence interval, the reference indicators of this indicator vary from 0.672 to 0.879. Cathelicidin's area on the ROC curve is 0.855;

its standard error is 0.042 ($p < 0.001$). Cathelicidin reference values range from 0.773 to 0.937 in the 95% confidence interval. The area of the mean is 0.794 and the standard error is 0.050 ($p < 0.001$), with a lower and upper limit of 0.697-892 at the 95% confidence interval (picture 1.1.).

Picture 1.1. ROC analysis of Cathelicidin

Thus, according to the results of ROC statistical analysis, AMP, Calprotectin, and cathelicidin can be considered tests with high informativeness and specificity. The obtained results prove the role of AMP in the pathogenesis and immune mechanisms of CRC. Determination of these indicators is of great practical importance in determining the malignancy, stage, and degree of severity of the disease.

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PREDICTIVE IMMUNOLOGICAL MARKERS IN COLORECTAL CANCER DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

Recently, immune mechanisms in the pathogenesis of colorectal cancer have been the focus of special attention and are widely studied. Cytokines and antimicrobial peptides (AMP) play an important regulatory role in immune mechanisms. According to the results of many studies, cytokines play an important role in the monitoring and prognosis of malignant oncological diseases. The concentration of Calprotectin in the blood serum of patients in group II was higher than control limits in 13 patients (92.0%) and lower than control in 1 patient (8.0%) ($\chi=24.27$, $p<0.001$). Based on the obtained results, the concentration of Calprotectin increases statistically reliably by 3.5 times compared to the control group, and the coefficient of the integrity of this difference is $p<0.001$. The average mathematical density of this indicator is 3.42 ± 0.48 pg/ml, the minimum density is 0.7 pg/ml, and the maximum thickness is 6.1 pg/ml.

Keywords: Colorectal cancer, Calprotectin, CEA, antimicrobial peptides.

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the most common cancers in the world. The incidence increases progressively after the age of 50. Its early diagnosis is difficult because of its usually remain asymptomatic. Colon cancer and rectal cancer are often grouped together because they have many features in common. Colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer worldwide, with nearly 1.4 million new cases diagnosed in 2012. The number of new cases of colon and rectum cancer was 40.1 per 100,000 men and women per year. The number of deaths was 14.8 per 100,000 men and women per year. These rates are age-adjusted and based in 2010-2014 cases of deaths. The present studies are made on adenocarcinomas, the most frequent histological type of colon cancer, which accounts for some 98% of all malignancies in the large bowel. The majority of adenocarcinomas occur sporadically (75-85%), but 25-30% of the patients have a family history of cancer. In about 5% of the CRC patients, an inherited germline gene defect is confirmed. The prognosis of CRC differs widely among patients, and depends on a number of factors. Currently, the gold standard of prognostication is the clinicopathological staging based on the TNM classification system. Stage of the disease at presentation has profound effect on the prognosis. Prognosis also differs between patients within the same TNM stage, and many clinical, histopathological and biomolecular markers have potential impact on outcome.

The purpose of this study is to quantify fecal and plasma Calprotectin and CEA levels in colorectal cancer, polyps and control patients and also to analyze the

differences between these groups and the diagnostic value of these markers. In addition, we aimed to assess the relationship between clinicopathologic variables for cancer and polyps and fecal and plasma Calprotectin, CEA levels. For working group, plasma samples were taken from 19 controls, 23 polyps, 64 cancer patients and fecal samples were taken from 16 controls, 8 polyps, 8 cancer. Male to female ratio was 30/34 with a mean age of 50 (30-81) for colorectal cancer group and male to female ratio was 10/9 with a mean age of 44 (31-56) for control group. Physical examinations, urinalysis, chest x-rays and abdominal ultrasonographies were performed to all patients in Colorectal cancer group. Blood samples were obtained before any treatment for Cal levels. Blood samples for control group were obtained from the collective of biochemistry department (Azerbaijan Medical University). No local, systemic inflammation or incarceration was observed in control group patients. Patients with normal leukocyte (WBC), C-reactive protein (CRP) values were included in the control group. Age, WBC glucose, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), CRP values of patients who has high plasma amylase and lipase were measured. For measuring plasma Cal values, blood samples were taken to biochemical tube and then aliquots of serum were stored at -80°C for assaying.

Previously the research was focused on different clinical and histopathological factors and a limited number of protein markers, such as CEA. Carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) is a glycoprotein involved in